

Continuous-Variable Quantum Key Distribution for Enabling Sustainable Secure 6G Networks

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Abstract—Several technological challenges are currently posed by future 6G networks to support ultra-high capacity and dynamic connectivity, while ensuring environmental and societal sustainability, scalability, and reliability. Among them, security is a crucial aspect, particularly considering open and disaggregated networks. Continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD) is proposed as an appealing solution to ensure long-term security, while facilitating the coexistence with conventional optical communications for a sustainable integration of QKD technology in future 6G networks. In this work, the adoption of CV-QKD in future optical networks is discussed, focusing on the network resources and infrastructure sharing, exploring advanced features, flexibility and programmability, further enabled by software defined networking (SDN).

Keywords—Continuous variable (CV), quantum key distribution (QKD), software defined networking (SDN), optical networks, 6G networks, coexistence.

I. INTRODUCTION

New technological challenges and critical requirements are posed by future 6G networks to ensure environmental and societal sustainability, reliability, and security, while supporting very high capacity/bandwidth connectivity. Modular and programmable advanced transceivers, such as the sliceable bandwidth/bitrate variable transceiver (S-BVT), are proposed to address dynamic multi-Tb/s connectivity, exploiting both ultrawideband (beyond the C-band) wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) and spatial division multiplexing (SDM) [1], [2]. In addition to strategies for optimal network resources usage and grow-as-needed approach, a shift towards open and disaggregated optical networks, decoupling hardware from software, is promoted by Telecom Operators to address interoperability and cost-efficiency [3]. This favors competitiveness and accessibility, thanks to the vendor-neutral approach and derived cost-reduction, resulting in a more sustainable network development. In this open scenario and to face the advent or threat of quantum computers, the design and implementation of efficient quantum secure communication appears to be a

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fundamental requirement to urgently address. Accordingly, the adoption of quantum key distribution (QKD) is proposed as a promising technology to ensure long-term security. In particular, continuous variable (CV) QKD is arising as an interesting option more compatible with optical networks, thanks to the adoption of optical coherent technology [4]. This enables the use of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components and photonic integrated circuits (PICs), drastically reducing the costs and favoring a sustainable adoption of QKD in future optical networks [5]. Software defined networking (SDN) further facilitates and possibly accelerates the adoption of this technology and its integration into the network infrastructure [6]. This is particularly relevant, especially when the deployment of a dedicated network for QKD is not feasible and coexistence of quantum and classical channels is required in the same fiber, to enable a sustainable transition towards quantum secure communications in support of 6G networks.

In this work, we discuss the adoption of CV-QKD in optical networks, and in synergy with SDN, for addressing the 6G challenges. Furthermore, flexible advanced features that can be enabled by the SDN controller are explored to promote bandwidth sharing and optimal network resources usage. We demonstrate that, by carefully designing the coexistence scenario and analyzing the related impairments, the quantum channel can be flexibly accommodated in co-propagation with classical channels.

II. CV-QKD IN OPTICAL NETWORKS

QKD allows two communication parties (Alice and Bob) to generate a secret key through a potentially insecure quantum channel. This relies on the laws of quantum mechanics; specifically, the fact that the observation of a quantum system causes perturbations on its quantum state. This means that any attack to the quantum channel performed by an eavesdropper (Eve) affects the exchanged information. A CV-QKD protocol employs coherent states (CS) as information carriers [7]. By modulating the optical fields, the signals carry information encoded in their quadratures (q, p).

A. Security of CV-QKD

The security of CV-QKD protocols against quantum channel attacks is evaluated by means of the secret key rate $K = f_{sym} \cdot r$. The symbol rate f_{sym} usually takes values of tens to hundreds of MHz and the secret fraction r corresponds to the final secret key length divided by the total number of exchanged signals. The secret fraction is defined by the

correlations in the information shared by Alice and Bob, as well as the information that Eve could have access to after a quantum channel attack. Hence, it is bounded as $r \geq \beta I_{AB} - S_{BE}$, where β is the reconciliation efficiency. The correlations are measured through I_{AB} , the classical Shannon mutual information between Alice's and Bob's data, and S_{BE} is the quantum mutual information between Bob's measured data and Eve's quantum state. Despite the quantity S_{BE} is in general difficult to compute, the Holevo information provides an upper bound that is asymptotically attainable with collective attacks. This can be obtained from the covariance matrix of the entanglement-based (EB) version of the protocol [7]. For the case of Gaussian modulated (GM) CS, the bound of the Holevo information simplifies, and it is determined by the modulation variance (V_{mod}), the channel transmittance (T) and the excess noise (ξ). Note that T is a fixed value determined by the channel length, the attenuation rate as well as both detection and coupling efficiencies, while V_{mod} could be optimized. Moreover, ξ could be rigorously modeled even before the protocol starts, to assess the parameter estimation procedure [7]. For protocols with non-Gaussian modulation, however, the argument still applies given that the bipartite quantum state shared by Alice and Bob in the EB protocol is close to a Gaussian state. Particularly, this is the case of protocols featuring discrete modulation in the low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) regime [8]. This is relevant since, for long channel lengths, where the SNR becomes significantly small, discrete modulation protocols are known to outperform their Gaussian counterpart. Furthermore, Gaussian optimality is conjectured to still apply in a non-asymptotic scenario. Therefore, by considering the possible errors at each stage of the protocol that affect the overall security, a robust and composable model for the secret fraction in the finite-size regime can be provided, given that the quantum state is at least close to a Gaussian state [9], [10].

B. Coexistence of quantum and classical channels

The envisioned coexistence scenario is presented in Fig. 1. A set of high-capacity BVTs is considered. The BVT transceiver (Tx) / receiver (Rx) set can possibly adopt a multi-flow aggregator/distributor (indicated with dashed line) to implement a S-BVT, enabling also point-to-multipoint transmission [1], [2]. Multiplexing in both the spectral (DWDM) and spatial (SDM) domains can be envisioned for co-propagating the quantum and classical channels, fully exploiting the network resources. The CV-QKD system is based on Gaussian modulation of coherent states (GMCS) and adopts a phase diversity coherent receiver (CO-Rx).

Fig. 1. Coexistence scenario; in the insets, details of CV-QKD transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx).

In [6], we experimentally assessed the capability of a CV-QKD system to tune the wavelength of the quantum channel over the C-band, in steps of 200 GHz. Here, we analyze the impact of minimizing the channel spacing in order to suitably accommodate the quantum signal, for optimizing the network resources in terms of bandwidth, in coexistence with classical channels at 200 Gb/s. In particular, we consider the coexistence scenario of Fig. 1, where the set of BVTs consists of eight classical transceivers, generating dual-polarized (DP) signals with 16-QAM modulation format and symbol rate of 32 Gbaud. The CV-QKD Tx employs a laser as a coherent light source with phase modulator (PM) and amplitude modulator (AM) to generate optical pulses with amplitude and phase modulation based on a random Gaussian distribution (q , p). A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is adopted to suitably attenuate the signal to the photon level and adjust V_{mod} . The quantum and classical channels are multiplexed in the frequency domain with a multiplexer (Mux) and transmitted over a standard single-mode fiber (SMF). Before entering the phase diversity homodyne CO-Rx (see the inset of Fig. 1), the CV-QKD signal is extracted using a bandpass filter. In the VPIphotonics [11] set-up, used for the assessment, the local oscillator (LO) is derived from the transmitter laser adopting a beam splitter. In practical systems, a true LO must be used to avoid security breach. Finally, a parameter estimation process is performed.

Fig. 2. Impact of quantum and classical channels spacing (guard-band) on the KQD system performance, in terms of ξ and r , over 10 km SMF link.

For the performance evaluation, we analyze the parameters ξ and r at the varying of the quantum and classical channels spacing. The excess noise can be expressed as $\xi = \xi_o + \xi_{NLI}$, where ξ_o represents the intrinsic noise of the CV-QKD system and ξ_{NLI} accounts for the fiber nonlinearity noise, including spontaneous Raman scattering (SRS), self-phase modulation (SPM), cross-phase modulation (XPM), and four-wave mixing (FWM). The intrinsic noise ξ_o is modeled according to [7] and is calculated at 0.046 shot-noise-units (SNU) for a 10 km SMF link. Assuming detection and coupling efficiency to be 1, a fixed V_{mod} value of 6 SNU has been considered to balance the trade-off between fiber reach and excess noise at the Rx, taking into account the transmission impairments from the photonic hardware [6]. The nonlinear effects, adding extra noise and significantly degrading the KQD performance, have been taken into account and modelled, according to the VPIphotonics fiber model [11]. Fig. 2 illustrates the performance in terms of ξ and r , as functions of the guard-band (classical-quantum channel spacing), for a 10 km SMF link. The inset displays the coexistence spectrum, with the quantum signal at 193.4 THz and four classical signals, each 100 GHz apart, on both sides. The total launch power for the classical channels is fixed to 8 mW (9 dBm). With 100 GHz quantum-classical channel

spacing, ξ has a value above 5 SNU and r is negative, indicating that key generation is not possible. However, for guard-bands exceeding 135 GHz, r becomes positive and increases notably, achieving its maximum values for channel spacing larger than 150 GHz. As expected, higher excess noise values are obtained with smaller guard-bands, suggesting that the noise accounting for the nonlinear effects has a more significant impact, when the CV-QKD signal is close to the classical channels.

III. SDN-ENABLED CV-QKD

SDN has a crucial relevance to further accelerate the adoption of QKD within the network infrastructure and to suitably configure and manage the QKD nodes in a coexistence scenario. Fig. 3 shows the SDN-enabled coexistence scenario presented in Fig. 1. SDN also allows enabling flexible and advanced features, such as the tunability of the quantum channel wavelength of a CV-QKD system.

Fig. 3. SDN-enabled CV-QKD in coexistence with programmable S-BVT. Relevant interfaces are indicated.

A. Programmability and relevant interfaces

The fundamental building block of the QKD network architecture is the software-defined QKD (SD-QKD) node. It consists of one or multiple QKD modules (optoelectronic Tx and Rx), the key management system (KMS) and the SD-QKD node controller (also referred to as SDN QKD agent). The most relevant interfaces are i) the ETSI GS QKD 004 or 014, connecting the QKD module with the KMS, and ii) the south bound interface (SBI) ETSI GS QKD 015, communicating the SD-QKD network controller with the SD-QKD node controller, enabling configuration and monitoring of the SD-QKD node [6]. The SD-optical network controller coordinates both the SDN-enabled S-BVTs, by means of the agents and the suitable SBI (e.g., OpenConfig open data model), and the SDN optical line system (OLS) controller. Finally, the SDN orchestrator is in charge of orchestrating both the SD optical and QKD network controllers.

B. Flexibility and advanced programmable functionalities

A relevant advanced feature that can be enabled by the SD-QKD node controller in a QKD network, where the QKD modules are based on CV-QKD, is the flexible tuning of the quantum channel wavelength. According to the coexistence scenario, the appropriate channel wavelength and spacing can be selected in order to suitably accommodate the quantum channel, ensuring key generation in presence of classical channels. Similarly, classical channels generated at the S-BVT can be enabled/disabled and their power adjusted, by

means of the SDN S-BVT agent, for ensuring the coexistence with the quantum channel. Coordinated actions, thanks to the SDN orchestrator, enable optimal resource usage and quantum secure communication in coexistence with classical channels within the network infrastructure.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A synergy of CV-QKD and SDN enables resource sharing in coexistence with classical optical systems, leveraging the existing infrastructure and, thus, significantly reducing the cost while easing the introduction of this quantum technology in future networks. Despite classical channels co-propagation has a large impact on the QKD channel performance, considering a sufficiently large guard-band, key generation is possible. We have found that, with a minimum spacing of the quantum channel from the classical channels of 135 GHz, the secret key rate assumes positive value and, with guard-band above 150 GHz, it can be maximized, in presence of up to eight data channels at 200 Gb/s with a total power of 9 dBm. Thanks to the CV-QKD system capability of flexibly tuning the operating wavelength within the C-band, it can be suitably configured by the SD-QKD controller, according to the coexistence scenario, easing the accommodation of quantum channels in the optical network. These results are promising in support of future sustainable and secure 6G networks.

Future work on the coexistence of CV-QKD with SDN-enabled S-BVT, its impact on the performance and possible mitigation and/or optimal allocation strategies, as well as on the SD-QKD network controller for a smooth integration and application in 6G networks are envisioned in the framework of the Horizon Europe ALLEGRO project and the UNICO 5G I+D 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS project.

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